

Caveman Compression: MLM-Guided Token Removal for Reducing LLM Inference Costs

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Abstract. Reducing input tokens for Large Language Model (LLM) inference directly decreases cost and latency, but existing compression methods—extractive summarization, abstractive rewriting, learned compression—either risk information loss, introduce hallucination, or require task-specific training. This paper proposes that natural language can be compressed by removing high-predictability tokens while preserving low-predictability tokens carrying essential information, as LLMs can internally reconstruct predictable linguistic scaffolding (articles, connectives) from context. This paper presents one concrete implementation using Masked Language Models (MLMs) to score token predictability, enhanced with linguistic protection to preserve factual anchors regardless of predictability: Named Entity Recognition (NER) protects names, dates, and quantities, while compound noun detection preserves semantically linked word pairs (e.g., “calcium carbonate”, “climate change”). Evaluating on 79 diverse topics (948 questions), the method achieves 29% token reduction with 96% mean accuracy at probability threshold $P \geq 10^{-5}$. At aggressive settings ($P \geq 10^{-6}$), compression reaches 50% with 91% mean accuracy. At conservative settings ($P \geq 10^{-3}$), 85% of topics achieve baseline-parity (100% accuracy), and the median accuracy is 100%. Comparison against baselines on fiction topics shows MLM-guided compression substantially outperforms both random token removal (98.9% vs 84.2% at 14% reduction) and stopword removal (93.9% vs 77.8% at comparable compression). NER protection improves accuracy retention at aggressive thresholds with minimal compression trade-off. Results depend on importance-aware token selection and are specific to English expository text evaluated with an LLM-as-judge framework. The method is training-free, deterministic, and applicable to any LLM application requiring input reduction. These results suggest that importance-aware deletion of high-predictability tokens is a practical, low-overhead tool for reducing inference costs across LLM applications, including RAG systems, conversation history compression, and other pipelines requiring context reduction. Code and data are available at <https://github.com/wilpel/caveman-compression-benchmark>.

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated strong capabilities in natural language understanding and generation tasks. However, the computational cost of LLM inference scales linearly with input token count. Most LLM providers charge per token, making input compression relevant for reducing computational cost. Additionally, context window limitations pose practical constraints even for models with large theoretical limits. While some models support 128K or 200K token contexts, filling these windows incurs substantial computational cost and latency.

Natural language contains substantial redundancy—many words are predictable from context and carry minimal unique information. Traditional compression approaches such as LLM-based rewriting and extractive summarization have trade-offs: rewriting introduces latency and hallucination risks, while extractive methods may lose critical details by discarding entire sentences. The ideal compression method would be fast, deterministic, context-aware, and preserve all semantically critical information while removing only redundant linguistic scaffolding.

This work introduces Caveman Compression, a conceptual framework proposing that natural language can be aggressively compressed by remov-

ing high-predictability tokens while preserving low-predictability tokens. The central hypothesis is that LLMs possess sufficient language understanding to internally reconstruct or infer highly predictable linguistic elements from context, making explicit inclusion of such tokens unnecessary for comprehension. When encountering compressed text with missing articles, prepositions, or other grammatical scaffolding, the LLM can leverage its learned language patterns to process the text as if the missing tokens were present. Conversely, tokens with low predictability carry essential information content that cannot be reliably inferred and must be preserved.

This paper presents one concrete implementation using Masked Language Models (MLMs). The method leverages RoBERTa to compute contextual predictability scores— $P(w \mid \text{context})$ —for each token. High-probability tokens carry less unique information and are candidates for removal. The approach removes all tokens whose probability exceeds a threshold P , eliminating linguistic scaffolding while maintaining informational density. To prevent removal of factually critical tokens that happen to appear in predictable contexts, the method incorporates two linguistic protection mechanisms: Named Entity Recognition (NER) preserves names, dates, quantities, and other entities; compound noun detection preserves semantically

linked word pairs where the modifier is predictable but essential (e.g., “calcium” in “calcium carbonate”, “climate” in “climate change”). This combined approach is simple yet effective, requiring no training while achieving substantial compression with minimal quality degradation.

Contributions. This paper makes the following contributions:

1. We propose Caveman Compression, an MLM-guided token removal framework with NER and compound noun protection that requires no task-specific training.
2. We demonstrate on 79 topics (948 questions) that the method achieves 15–50% token reduction with 91–98% accuracy retention, depending on threshold selection.
3. We show that importance-aware token selection outperforms random deletion by 14.7 percentage points and stopword removal by 16.1 percentage points at comparable compression ratios.
4. We release a curated RAG question-answering dataset and open-source implementation to support reproducibility.

2 Related Work

Prior work on prompt compression falls into two categories. *Hard prompt* methods remove discrete tokens while preserving natural language structure. LLM-Lingua [Jiang et al., 2023] and its successor [Jiang et al., 2024] use causal language model perplexity to identify and remove low-information tokens, achieving up to 20x compression. Selective Context [Li et al., 2023] similarly uses self-information metrics for token pruning. RECOMP [Xu et al., 2024] operates at the sentence level, training extractive compressors for retrieval-augmented generation. *Soft prompt* methods such as AutoCompressors [Chevalier et al., 2023] and Gist tokens [Mu et al., 2023] compress context into continuous embeddings, achieving higher compression ratios but requiring model fine-tuning and producing representations incompatible with black-box APIs.

The approach presented here differs in several respects. Unlike LLM-Lingua and Selective Context, which use unidirectional causal LM perplexity, this method uses bidirectional MLM probability through RoBERTa [Liu et al., 2019], capturing both preceding and following context. Unlike soft prompt methods, the output remains natural language compatible with any LLM. Unlike RECOMP, compression operates at token granularity, preserving document structure. The method requires no training—only inference through a pre-trained MLM—and is evaluated on RAG question-answering tasks [Lewis et al., 2020] using downstream accuracy rather than proxy metrics.

3 Method

3.1 Problem Formulation

Let $D = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ be a document of n words, and let $Q = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m\}$ be a set of questions answerable from D . Define a compression operator $\mathcal{C}_P : D \rightarrow D'$ parameterized by threshold P , which selectively removes words based on two criteria: (1) predictability—words with $P(w \mid \text{context}) \geq P$ are candidates for removal; and (2) linguistic protection—words are preserved regardless of predictability if they are named entities (persons, organizations, locations, dates, quantities) or components of compound nouns (e.g., “calcium” in “calcium carbonate”). The compressed document $D' = \mathcal{C}_P(D)$ satisfies $|D'| < |D|$.

Evaluation metrics. We measure compression quality through downstream task performance:

- *Raw accuracy:* $\text{Acc}_{\text{raw}}(D', Q) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbf{1}[\text{correct}(q_i, D')]$
- *Token reduction:* $\text{Red}(D, D') = 1 - \frac{|D'|}{|D|}$
- *Accuracy retention:* $\text{Ret}(D, D', Q) = \frac{\text{Acc}(D', Q)}{\text{Acc}(D, Q)} \times 100\%$

Baseline-parity. A topic achieves *baseline-parity* under compression when $\text{Acc}(D', Q) = \text{Acc}(D, Q)$ —the compressed document yields the same accuracy as the original. This is a topic-level metric; individual questions may differ.

The optimization goal is to maximize token reduction while maintaining high accuracy retention, with baseline-parity representing the ideal case of no accuracy loss.

3.2 MLM-Based Predictability Scoring

For each word w_i in document D , the predictability is computed using RoBERTa, a bidirectional masked language model.

Masking. The target word w_i is replaced with a [MASK] token while keeping all surrounding context intact. For example, “The cat sat on the mat” becomes “The cat sat on [MASK] mat” when scoring the second “the”.

Prediction. The masked sentence is passed through RoBERTa, which outputs a probability distribution over its entire vocabulary for the masked position, representing how likely each possible word is given the surrounding context.

Scoring. The predictability score $P(w_i \mid \text{context})$ is extracted—the probability RoBERTa assigns to the *original* word appearing at that position. A high probability (e.g., $P = 0.8$) means RoBERTa confidently predicts the word from context, indicating it carries little unique information. A low probability (e.g., $P = 10^{-6}$) means the word is surprising given its context, indicating it likely carries essential information.

This scoring is performed independently for every word in the document, with punctuation excluded

Figure 1: Compression pipeline combining MLM predictability scoring with linguistic protection. Step 2a computes $P(\text{word}|\text{context})$ via RoBERTa; Step 2b identifies named entities and compound nouns via spaCy. Step 3 removes tokens only if they exceed the probability threshold *and* are not protected. Named entities and compound noun components are preserved regardless of predictability, while high-probability function words are removed.

from consideration. Figure 1 illustrates the complete pipeline.

3.3 Token Selection and Removal

After scoring all words, removal decisions combine probability thresholding with linguistic protection. A word w_i is removed if and only if: (1) its predictability exceeds the threshold, $P(w_i | \text{context}) \geq P$; and (2) it is not linguistically protected. The intuition: if RoBERTa can predict a word with high probability, an LLM reading the compressed text can likely infer it—but certain word classes carry irreplaceable content even when syntactically predictable.

Named entity protection. Using spaCy’s NER pipeline, we protect entities across three categories: proper nouns (person names, organizations, geopolitical entities), temporal expressions (dates, times), and numeric values (money, percentages, quantities). For example, in “John visited Microsoft in Seattle”, the name “John” might score high probability due to common sentence patterns, yet removing it loses critical information.

Compound noun protection. Compound nouns consist of modifier-head pairs where the modifier is often highly predictable given the head, yet essential for meaning. Using spaCy’s dependency parser, we identify tokens with the compound dependency relation and protect both the modifier and its head. For example, “calcium” in “calcium carbonate” scores high probability (the MLM expects it before “carbonate”), but removing it changes the meaning entirely—“carbonate” alone does not convey the same chemical compound. Similarly, “climate” in “climate change”, “fecal” in “fecal matter”, and “mixed” in “mixed-use” are all predictable modifiers that carry essential semantic content. Without compound noun protection, these dele-

Figure 2: Linguistic protection example. Orange: compound nouns (“climate change”) preserved despite high P . Blue: named entities (Seattle/GPE, March 2024/DATE) preserved. Red dashed: removed (“affects”, “and”).

tions cause downstream task failures. Figure 2 illustrates this protection mechanism.

Example. Given “Robots are used in factories to assemble cars and electronics” with scores:

Word	$P(w \text{context})$	Word	$P(w \text{context})$
Robots	2.1×10^{-7}	to	2.9×10^{-6}
are	1.3×10^{-5}	assemble	3.0×10^{-10}
used	2.2×10^{-8}	cars	3.7×10^{-7}
in	1.0×10^{-6}	and	1.8×10^{-6}
factories	3.0×10^{-10}	electronics	5.3×10^{-10}

No named entities are detected in this sentence (all common nouns). With threshold $P \geq 10^{-5}$, only “are” ($P = 1.3 \times 10^{-5}$) exceeds the threshold and is removed, yielding: “Robots used in factories to assemble cars and electronics”. With a more aggressive threshold $P \geq 10^{-6}$, the words “are”, “in”, “to”, and “and” are removed, yielding: “Robots used factories assemble cars electronics”.

Lower thresholds remove more words (aggressive compression, higher information loss risk). Higher thresholds are conservative, preserving more content. NER protection reduces compression ratio slightly (2–3%) but improves accuracy retention, particularly at aggressive thresholds.

3.4 Complexity and Practical Considerations

The algorithm requires $O(n)$ masked forward passes through RoBERTa for a document with n words—one pass per word to compute its predictability score. This linear scaling is acceptable for offline preprocessing but may be prohibitive for real-time applications.

Information-theoretic interpretation. Probability thresholds correspond to surprisal bounds. By Shannon’s theory, surprisal $I(w) = -\log_2 P(w | \text{context})$ measures information in bits. Our thresholds map to:

Threshold P	Surprisal \leq (bits)
10^{-3}	10.0
10^{-4}	13.3
10^{-5}	16.6
10^{-6}	19.9

Tokens exceeding threshold P carry $\leq -\log_2 P$ bits of information and are removed. Detailed timing benchmarks and cost-benefit analysis are deferred to Discussion.

4 Experiments

4.1 Dataset

A diverse dataset of 79 topics was curated spanning science, technology, arts, humanities, and fiction, representing real-world RAG use cases. The dataset comprises 47 factual topics (59.5%) covering technical documentation, scientific explanations, and reference material, alongside 32 fictional topics (40.5%) with entirely invented characters, locations, and events to control for training data contamination. Each topic contains 150–800 tokens (mean: 423, $\sigma = 156$) with 12 questions per topic.

Difficulty stratification. Questions are divided into three difficulty levels (4 per level per topic): *Easy* questions test direct recall of explicit facts—specific numbers, names, dates, or measurements stated verbatim in the text. *Medium* questions test procedural understanding—sequences of steps, causal relationships, or how components interact. *Hard* questions require reasoning and synthesis—integrating multiple facts, drawing inferences, or explaining why something works. This stratification enables analysis of how compression affects different cognitive demands.

Question types. Questions span five categories: factual (direct lookup), process (sequential steps), reasoning (causal inference), consequence (what happens if), and synthesis (combining multiple facts). Each topic includes a mix of types to ensure comprehensive coverage.

Curation process. Questions and ground truth answers were initially generated using Claude 4 Sonnet, then manually reviewed and edited by the author. All 948 question-answer pairs were individually verified, with ambiguous, unanswerable, or poorly-phrased items revised or replaced. The final dataset reflects human curation rather than raw LLM output.

Data availability. The complete dataset, including all topic texts, questions, answers, and metadata, is released alongside the code at <https://github.com/wilpel/caveman-compression-benchmark>. All factual topics were authored or compiled from public domain sources; fictional topics are original creations. The dataset is released under the MIT license for research use.

Evaluation spans 948 total questions at four probability thresholds ($P \in \{10^{-6}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}\}$), yielding 3,792 total evaluation instances.

4.2 Models & Implementation

Four components serve distinct roles in the pipeline:

Scorer. RoBERTa-base [Liu et al., 2019] (125M parameters) computes predictability scores via masked language modeling. For each word position, the word is replaced with [MASK] and RoBERTa outputs a probability distribution over its vocabulary; we extract $P(w | \text{context})$ for the original word.

Linguistic Protector. spaCy’s `en_core_web_sm` model (12M parameters) provides both NER (named

entity recognition) and dependency parsing for compound noun detection. Protected entity types include PERSON, ORG, GPE, DATE, TIME, MONEY, PERCENT, QUANTITY, and CARDINAL.

Answerer. OpenAI’s GPT-5 (accessed via API, November 2025) answers questions from compressed context. The model receives a system prompt instructing it to answer only from the provided context, followed by the compressed text and question. Temperature is set to 0.1 for reproducibility. Full prompts are included in the code repository.

Judge. Anthropic’s Claude 4 Sonnet (accessed via API, November 2025) evaluates answer correctness, using a different model family to mitigate evaluation bias. The judge receives the question, expected answer, and actual answer, and outputs a JSON response with a boolean correctness judgment and brief explanation. Using a separate model family for evaluation reduces the risk of systematic biases that might arise from using the same model for both answering and judging.

Tokenizer handling. Predictability scoring operates at the word level: text is split on whitespace, and each word is scored independently using RoBERTa’s BPE tokenizer. Token counting for cost metrics uses tiktoken with `cl100k_base` encoding (GPT tokenization). Removal decisions are made at word boundaries; the tokenizer mismatch affects only the mapping between probability scores and final token counts, not which words are removed.

All models are used in their pretrained form without fine-tuning. The compression process is deterministic and reproducible. Implementation code, prompts, and evaluation scripts are available at <https://github.com/wilpel/caveman-compression-benchmark>.

4.3 Evaluation Protocol

The evaluation pipeline operates as follows: (1) compress the document using the method under test, (2) prompt GPT-5 to answer each question using only the compressed context, and (3) judge answer correctness using Claude 4 Sonnet.

Answer validation uses semantic equivalence rather than exact string matching. The judge receives the question, expected answer, and generated answer, then outputs a structured JSON response: `{"correct": true/false, "explanation": "..."}.` The judge is prompted to accept paraphrased answers that convey the same factual content, while rejecting answers that omit key details, contain factual errors, or fail to address the question.

All results report **raw accuracy**: the fraction of questions answered correctly end-to-end. This conservative metric reflects real-world deployment where the source of errors (compression vs. extraction) is indistinguishable to the end user. Metrics are defined formally in §3.1.

Table 1: Compression performance with linguistic protection (NER + compound nouns) across 79 topics (948 questions). Raw accuracy reported. Parity = topics achieving 100% accuracy.

Threshold P	Reduction	Accuracy	Parity
$\geq 10^{-3}$	15.1%	98.4%	84.8%
$\geq 10^{-4}$	18.3%	98.0%	79.7%
$\geq 10^{-5}$	29.4%	95.9%	58.2%
$\geq 10^{-6}$	49.8%	90.8%	43.0%

Figure 3: Accuracy versus token reduction trade-off. Each point represents a probability threshold, with lower thresholds yielding more aggressive compression. Performance degrades gracefully from 98% accuracy at 15% reduction to 91% accuracy at 50% reduction.

4.4 Main Results

Table 1 summarizes key operating points. Figure 3 illustrates the trade-off between token reduction and accuracy retention.

The performance curve reveals graceful degradation: token reduction increases as the probability threshold decreases, while accuracy decreases more slowly. Notably, at conservative thresholds ($P \geq 10^{-3}$ and $P \geq 10^{-4}$), the median accuracy is 100%—meaning *more than half* of all topics achieve baseline-parity. The lower mean is driven by a small number of outlier topics that are more sensitive to compression.

Variance. The distribution of per-topic accuracy is right-skewed: most topics cluster near 100%, with a tail of lower-performing topics pulling down the mean. At $P \geq 10^{-5}$, the interquartile range spans approximately 83–100% accuracy. Figures do not include error bars as each point represents a fixed threshold applied deterministically across all topics; variance arises from topic heterogeneity rather than stochastic estimation. Future work could report bootstrap confidence intervals over topic subsamples to characterize uncertainty in mean accuracy estimates.

Figure 4: Token reduction and baseline-parity rates by probability threshold. At conservative settings ($P \geq 10^{-3}$), 85% of topics maintain baseline-parity; aggressive compression ($P \geq 10^{-6}$) achieves 50% reduction.

4.5 Baseline-Parity Analysis

A notable finding is that many topics achieve baseline-parity—compressed accuracy equals uncompressed baseline accuracy—despite token removal. Figure 4 shows the distribution across different probability thresholds.

At $P \geq 10^{-3}$, 85% of topics (67/79) achieve baseline-parity with 15% compression. At $P \geq 10^{-4}$, 80% maintain baseline-parity with 18% reduction. Even at aggressive $P \geq 10^{-6}$, achieving 50% compression, 43% of topics retain baseline-parity.

This high baseline-parity rate has practical implications: for many topics under importance-aware compression, the removed tokens do not affect downstream task performance. The topics that fail to achieve baseline-parity tend to contain unusual proper nouns, technical jargon with predictable surrounding context, or peripheral details expressed in highly formulaic language. Importantly, even when compression does not achieve baseline-parity, the accuracy degradation is typically small—often a single question missed out of twelve.

4.6 Difficulty Analysis

An unexpected finding emerges when analyzing performance across difficulty levels (Figure 5). Contrary to intuition, harder questions often maintain comparable or higher accuracy under compression than easier questions. This pattern persists across threshold levels tested, though the effect size is modest.

A plausible explanation is that hard questions typically test core concepts and central themes that appear repeatedly throughout the text, resulting in lower average predictability scores for those tokens. Conversely, easy questions often test specific peripheral details (exact numbers, times, names) that may appear only once or in highly predictable contexts, making them more vulnerable to removal. However, this interpretation is tentative: the analysis does not control for baseline

Figure 5: Accuracy by question difficulty across probability thresholds. Hard questions show resilience to compression relative to easy questions, though confidence intervals overlap.

Table 2: Baseline comparison on 16 fiction topics. MLM compression substantially outperforms both random deletion and stopword removal at comparable compression ratios.

Method	Reduction	Accuracy
<i>MLM-guided (ours)</i>		
$P \geq 10^{-3}$	11.4%	98.3%
$P \geq 10^{-4}$	13.4%	98.9%
$P \geq 10^{-5}$	22.5%	93.9%
$P \geq 10^{-6}$	40.4%	90.6%
<i>Baselines</i>		
Random 15%	14.0%	84.2%
Random 30%	29.5%	71.1%
Stopword	32.7%	77.8%

difficulty (uncompressed accuracy by difficulty level), and selection effects may contribute. A more rigorous analysis would include per-difficulty baseline accuracy, confidence intervals, and random-drop controls to verify that importance-aware selection specifically protects core concepts.

4.7 Baseline Comparisons

To validate that MLM-guided token selection outperforms naive compression strategies, we compare against two baselines on a matched subset of 16 fiction topics (avoiding potential training data contamination):

Random removal. Tokens are removed uniformly at random at fixed rates (15% and 30%), with punctuation preserved. Random seed is fixed per topic for reproducibility.

Stopword removal. All tokens marked as stopwords by spaCy’s built-in lexicon (`token.is_stop`) are removed. This represents a simple rule-based baseline requiring no learned model.

Table 2 and Figure 6 reveal substantial performance gaps. At comparable compression ratios around 14%, MLM achieves 98.9% accuracy versus 84.2% for ran-

Figure 6: Baseline comparison on 16 fiction topics. MLM-guided compression (black) substantially outperforms random removal (hatched) and stopword removal (gray) at all compression levels. At comparable $\sim 14\%$ reduction, MLM achieves 98.9% vs random’s 84.2% accuracy.

dom removal—a 14.7 percentage point improvement. At higher compression around 30%, MLM ($P \geq 10^{-5}$) achieves 93.9% accuracy at 22.5% reduction, while stopword removal achieves only 77.8% at 32.7% reduction and random 30% achieves 71.1%. Even at aggressive 40% compression, MLM maintains 90.6% accuracy—higher than either baseline achieves at any compression level tested.

These results confirm that the performance gains stem from importance-aware token selection rather than mere token count reduction. Random deletion destroys information indiscriminately, while stopword removal applies a fixed vocabulary-based filter that fails to account for context—removing “the” before a unique proper noun loses different information than removing “the” in “the end”. MLM scoring captures these contextual distinctions, preserving tokens that carry high information content regardless of their surface form.

5 Discussion

5.1 Theoretical Foundation

The effectiveness of Caveman Compression stems from a fundamental hypothesis: LLMs have sufficient internalized knowledge of language patterns to reconstruct missing high-predictability tokens during inference, while low-predictability tokens carry irreplaceable information. As discussed in §3.4, this aligns with information-theoretic principles—highly predictable tokens carry minimal information content.

Empirically, content words exhibit lower predictability than function words, aligning predictability scores with semantic importance. By removing tokens exceeding the probability threshold P , the method predominantly eliminates function words while preserving content words—numbers, names, dates, technical terminology, and semantic constraints.

The bidirectional nature of MLM scoring is crucial. Unlike causal language models that only see preceding context, RoBERTa considers both left and right context when computing $P(w \mid \text{context})$. This means a word like “the” before a common noun scores high because RoBERTa sees both what comes before *and* the noun that follows. This bidirectional view provides more accurate predictability estimates than unidirectional approaches.

5.2 Why LLMs Can Process Compressed Text

A natural question arises: if tokens are removed, won’t the LLM struggle to parse the compressed text? Prior work on prompt compression demonstrates that LLMs can tolerate substantial token removal with only modest performance degradation, *provided tokens are selected using importance-aware methods* [Jiang et al., 2023, Li et al., 2023]. LLMingua achieves up to 20x compression with minimal performance loss on question answering and summarization tasks; results may differ for tasks requiring precise syntactic structure.

Several factors may explain this tolerance in our setting. Natural language is highly redundant: core meaning is primarily encoded in content words and their relative order, while many function words provide grammatical structure that partly overlaps with other cues. Shannon’s foundational work established that English has approximately 75% redundancy [Shannon, 1948], a property that supports both human error correction and, we hypothesize, LLM robustness to missing tokens. Additionally, LLMs are trained on massive heterogeneous corpora including noisy, incomplete, and informal text, and their training objective—predicting masked or next tokens—implicitly teaches them to infer missing material from context. Self-attention mechanisms may further allow models to connect semantically related content words directly, even when grammatical scaffolding is absent.

However, this tolerance has limits. Robustness depends critically on *which* tokens are removed: dropping low-predictability content words or logically important function words (negation, quantifiers, modals) degrades performance substantially. The success of compression thus depends on intelligent token selection, which probability-based scoring aims to provide. Random token removal at equivalent compression ratios would likely yield substantially worse results.

5.3 Limitations

Computational overhead. Computing MLM probabilities requires a forward pass through RoBERTa for each word position (masking and scoring each word independently), resulting in $O(n)$ forward passes for a document with n words. For a typical 400-word document, this requires approximately 400 RoBERTa forward passes. On CPU, this introduces several seconds of latency per document; GPU acceleration and batched inference can reduce this substantially. The

preprocessing cost is best amortized when documents are accessed multiple times, as in RAG knowledge bases where a document may serve hundreds of queries. For single-access scenarios or streaming applications, the overhead may exceed the inference cost savings. A detailed cost-benefit analysis with measured wall-clock times across document lengths and hardware configurations would help practitioners determine breakeven points for their use cases.

Language dependence. The evaluation focuses on English informational text; optimal compression rates may differ for other languages with different grammatical structures, morphological complexity, or word order flexibility. Languages with rich inflectional morphology (e.g., Finnish, Turkish) or agglutinative structure may exhibit different predictability patterns. The threshold values identified here are specific to English and would require recalibration for other languages.

Domain sensitivity. While the evaluation spans diverse topics, highly specialized domains (legal contracts, medical records, mathematical proofs) may have different redundancy characteristics. Domains where precise wording carries legal or safety implications may not be suitable for lossy compression regardless of measured accuracy.

Threshold selection. The optimal threshold depends on the downstream task and acceptable accuracy trade-off. This paper provides empirical guidance, but production deployments would benefit from task-specific validation to select appropriate operating points.

5.4 Failure Modes

The primary failure mode involves exact phrasing requirements. When questions ask for verbatim quotes or precise wording, compression may remove words that don’t affect meaning but do affect exactness. Core semantic content is preserved, but stylistic or emphatic elements may be lost.

Empirically, the method tends to preserve semantically critical tokens. Negation words (“not”, “never”, “none”), numbers, and unusual proper nouns typically have low predictability scores because they dramatically change meaning and cannot be inferred from context. However, this preservation is not guaranteed: negation in highly formulaic contexts (e.g., “is not uncommon”) or numbers with predictable surrounding context may still be vulnerable. Systematic verification on targeted challenge sets (negation contrasts, quantifier substitutions, unit conversions) would strengthen confidence in robustness claims.

5.5 Threats to Validity

Several factors may affect the generalizability of these results:

Model-family coupling. The evaluation dataset was generated using Claude 4 Sonnet, answered using GPT-5, and judged using Claude 4 Sonnet. This cross-family design mitigates same-model bias, though

all models share similar training paradigms and may exhibit correlated biases. Human evaluation on a subset would further validate the results.

LLM-as-judge limitations. Semantic evaluation by an LLM may exhibit optimistic bias compared to human evaluation, particularly for paraphrased or partially correct answers.

Domain coverage. The evaluation focuses on English expository and fictional text. Domains where precise wording carries legal, medical, or safety implications (contracts, prescriptions, safety protocols) may exhibit different failure modes. Mathematical notation, source code, and structured data were excluded.

Tokenizer mismatch. MLM scoring uses RoBERTa’s BPE tokenizer while cost accounting uses GPT’s `cl100k_base` tokenizer. Tokens may align imperfectly across tokenizers, affecting which character spans are candidates for removal.

Language transfer. Optimal probability thresholds were calibrated for English. Languages with different morphological complexity (agglutinative, highly inflected) or word order flexibility may require different thresholds.

6 Conclusion

This paper presents Caveman Compression, a training-free approach to token reduction through MLM-guided removal enhanced with linguistic protection. The method leverages pre-trained masked language models to identify and remove redundant tokens while preserving task performance, with two protection mechanisms ensuring critical content is preserved: NER protection for factual anchors (names, dates, quantities), and compound noun protection for semantically linked word pairs where the modifier is predictable but essential. The approach is applicable to existing deployments without requiring model fine-tuning, architectural changes, or specialized infrastructure.

Evaluation across 79 diverse topics (948 questions) demonstrates that 15–50% token reduction is achievable with 91–98% accuracy retention, depending on threshold selection (Table 1). At conservative settings, 85% of topics achieve baseline-parity; even at aggressive 50% compression, over 40% maintain full accuracy. Baseline comparisons confirm that importance-aware selection substantially outperforms both random deletion and stopword removal at matched compression ratios (Table 2). Accuracy degrades gracefully with compression ratio, allowing applications to select operating points that balance accuracy requirements against cost savings.

The technique applies broadly to any LLM application where input text can be preprocessed before inference. Example use cases include RAG systems compressing retrieved documents, conversation history compression between LLM calls, document summarization pipelines, and batch processing workflows. These represent a subset of potential applications; the method is applicable wherever context reduction pro-

vides cost or latency benefits.

Future work spans several directions:

Comparisons. Head-to-head evaluation against LLMingua/LLMingua-2 and RECOMP at matched compression ratios.

Scorer variants. Comparing RoBERTa-base against smaller MLMs (DistilRoBERTa), causal LM pseudo-perplexity, and attention-based importance scores.

Adaptive policies. Content-aware threshold selection that varies P based on detected domain, topic importance, or token category.

Robustness & edge cases. Targeted challenge sets for negation, quantifiers, numbers, units, and code; systematic failure mode analysis.

Generalization. Cross-model studies with diverse LLM families; extension to multilingual contexts with language-specific threshold calibration.

The implementation is available as open source at <https://github.com/wilpel/caveman-compression-benchmark>.

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